

Diisothiocyanatodihalonickelates(II)

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Few diisothiocyanatodihalonickelates(II) $R_2[Ni(NCS)_2X_2]$ [$R = (C_6H_5)_4As$, $(C_6H_5)_4P$ or $(n-C_3H_7)_4N$ and $X = Cl$, Br or I] have been isolated from non-aqueous media and characterized by chemical analyses, melting points, molar conductance, ir and far ir and electronic spectral studies.

WE have been interested in the study of mixed halometallates viz., mixed haloantimonates(III)^{1,2} and mixed halocobaltates(II) and nickelates(II)³⁻⁶ and also substituted mixed halometallates of cobalt(II)⁷ and nickel(II)⁸. Simple tetrahalo- and tetraisothiocyanatonickelates(II) $(NiX_4)^{2-}$ ($X = Cl$, Br , I or SCN) are well known^{9,10} and there has also been reports on mixed tetrahalonickelates(II)^{11,12} but study on tetracoordinated nickelates(II) containing both halogens and thiocyanate groups is scanty¹³. In this article, we are reporting the isolation and ir, far ir and electronic spectral studies of $R_2[Ni(NCS)_2X_2]$ [$R = (n-C_3H_7)_4N$, $(C_6H_5)_4As$ or $(C_6H_5)_4P$ and $X = Cl$, Br or I].

Experimental

Preparation: These complexes were prepared by the interaction of nickel thiocyanate (prepared in absolute ethanol by the metathetical reaction of $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $KNCS$ (1 : 2) in presence of a small amount of triethylorthoformate) and R_4MX ($R = C_6H_5$ or $n-C_3H_7$; $M = N$, P or As and $X = Cl$, Br or I) in 1 : 2 molar ratio in a 2 : 1 (v/v) mixture of acetonitrile and absolute ethanol. The crystals thus obtained were recrystallised from acetonitrile, filtered, washed with a small amount of acetonitrile and then with ether and dried in an air oven at 90-100°.

Analyses: All the complexes were analysed for total thiocyanate plus halogen contents gravimetrically as $AgSCN$ plus AgX ($X = Cl$, Br or I) and also separately for thiocyanate contents by oxidizing SCN to sulphate by bromine water and precipitating as $BaSO_4$. Carbon and hydrogen were analysed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The melting points and analytical results are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements: Conductance measurements were carried out on $\sim 10^{-3} M$ solutions in nitromethane using a conductivity bridge made by PYE W.G. & Co. Ltd., (England). The electronic spectra were recorded as nujol mulls on Unicam SP 700 spectrophotometer. IR spectra ($400-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded as nujol mulls on Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer. The far ir spectra ($400-50\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded as nujol mulls using polythene discs on Perkin Elmer 180 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Conductance measurements: The molar conductance values ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) of these complexes (Table 1) (at $\sim 10^{-3} M$) in nitromethane (at $25 \pm 1^\circ$) fall within the generally acceptable range¹⁴ for 2 : 1 electrolytes ($\Lambda_M = 150-180$) indicating them to be 2 : 1 electrolytes.

IR spectra ($400-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$): The observed ν_{CN} ($\sim 2090\text{ cm}^{-1}$), ν_{CS} ($\sim 825\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and δ_{NCS}

TABLE 1 - ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MELTING POINTS AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$)

Compound	Elements present	% Found	% Calcd.	m. p. (°C)	Λ_M in $10^{-3} M$ CH_3NO_2
$[(C_6H_5)_4As]_2[Ni(NCS)_2Cl_2]$	C	58.8	59.3	224-6	172
	H	3.8	3.9		
	Cl	6.7	7.0		
	SCN	11.8	11.5		
$[(C_6H_5)_4As]_2[Ni(NCS)_2Br_2]$	C	55.2	54.5	254-6	175
	H	3.7	3.6		
	Br	14.1	14.5		
	SCN	10.6	10.5		
$[(C_6H_5)_4P]_2[Ni(NCS)_2Br_2]$	C	58.9	59.2	266-8	171
	H	3.6	3.9		
	Br	15.4	15.8		
	SCN	11.7	11.4		
$[(n-C_3H_7)_4N]_2[Ni(NCS)_2I_2]$	C	38.4	38.9	160-2	167
	H	7.2	7.0		
	I	30.2	31.7		
	SCN	14.2	14.5		

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (4000-400 cm⁻¹)

Compounds	δ NCS	ν CS	ν CN	2δ NCS
[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Cl ₂]*	—	820 m	2085 vs	952 w
[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Br ₂]*	—	825 m	2090 vs	952 w
[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ P] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Br ₂]	475	826 m	2091 vs	945 w
[(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₄ N] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ I ₂]	470 m	824 m	2092 vs	948 w

* δ NCS absorption is masked by strong absorption due to Ph₄As⁺ cation in this region.
m = medium, w = weak, vs = very strong.

(~470 cm⁻¹) frequencies (Table 2) occur in the frequency ranges¹⁰ suggested for the N-bonded thiocyanate ligand. The first overtone of NCS is also observed at ~950 cm⁻¹.

Far ir spectra: On the basis of C_{2v} symmetry of [Ni(NCS)₂X₂]²⁻ there should appear two Ni-X and two Ni-N stretching and one bending mode each for X-Ni-X and N-Ni-N. As regard the assignment for N-Ni-N bending mode there is no report even for [Ni(NCS)₂]²⁻ species¹⁵. Recently, Engelter and Thornton¹⁶ have assigned a band at 165 cm⁻¹ to N-Zn-N bending mode in ZnPy₂(NCS)₂ by applying isotopic substitution method. On this basis, in present case bands around 165 cm⁻¹ have been tentatively assigned to N-Ni-N bending mode. The band positions and their assignments are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FAR IR (400-50 cm⁻¹) SPECTRAL DATA

Compounds	Peak position	Assignment
A ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Cl ₂]	298 s	ν (Ni-Cl) + ν (Ni-N) cation
	283 s	
	236 m, 187 m	
	86 m, 71 ms	
	156 m	
P ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Br ₂]	127 w	δ (N-Ni-N)
	300 s, 277 s	δ (Cl-Ni-Cl)
	245 s, 238 sh	ν (Ni-N)
	267 m, 200 w	ν (Ni-Br)
	147 w, 70 m	cation
A ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ I ₂]	167 m	δ (N-Ni-N)
	84 w	δ (Br-Ni-Br)
	180 m	unassigned
	296 s, 276 s	ν (Ni-N)
	237 s, 224 sh	ν (Ni-Br)
Pr ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ I ₂]	202 m	unassigned
	164 w	δ (N-Ni-N)
	82 w	δ (Br-Ni-Br)
	182 m	cation
	297 s, b	ν (Ni-N)
A - (C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As ; P - (C ₆ H ₅) ₄ P ; Pr - (<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₄ N	198 s, b	ν (Ni-Cl)
	162 w	δ (N-Ni-N)
	70 m, 58 m	δ (I-Ni-I) or cation

A - (C₆H₅)₄As ; P - (C₆H₅)₄P ; Pr - (*n*-C₃H₇)₄N
s = strong ; ms = medium strong ; m = medium ; w = weak ; sh = shoulder ; b = broad.

In case of [Ni(NCS)₂Cl₂]²⁻ instead of the expected four stretching bands (two ν Ni-Cl and two ν Ni-N), only two broad bands are observed (298, 283 cm⁻¹) in this region, which may be due to the fact that ν Ni-N and ν Ni-Cl absorptions occur in nearly the same region of the spectrum^{15,17}.

However, it is not possible to distinguish as to which band is due to which vibration. The band at ~156 cm⁻¹ has been tentatively assigned to δ N-Ni-N¹⁶ and that at 127 cm⁻¹ to δ Cl-Ni-Cl¹⁷.

In case of [(C₆H₅)₄P]₂[Ni(NCS)₂Br₂], two bands at 300 and 277 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to two Ni-N and those at 245 and 238 cm⁻¹ to two Ni-Br stretching modes. These values are in good agreement with those reported for [Ni(NCS)₂]¹⁵ and (NiBr₄)²⁻ species^{15,17,18}. The bands at 167 and 86 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to δ N-Ni-N and δ Br-Ni-Br^{16,17}. Similar assignments could be made for [(C₆H₅)₄As]₂[Ni(NCS)₂Br₂] (Table 3).

In the spectrum of [Ni(NCS)₂I₂]²⁻ Ni-N and Ni-I stretching absorption bands do not show any splitting, instead they appear as single broad bands at 297 and 198 cm⁻¹ respectively. The weak band at 162 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to N-Ni-N bending mode^{16,17}, whereas those at 70 and 58 cm⁻¹ may be due to either I-Ni-I bending mode¹⁷ or cation, as the latter also absorbs in this region.

Electronic spectra: On the basis of C_{2v} symmetry of [Ni(NCS)₂X₂]²⁻, bands corresponding to the ν_1 and ν_3 transitions in tetrahedral Ni(II) should exhibit some splitting^{19,20}. But in the present case the visible region bands (ν_3) (14800-16200 cm⁻¹) (Table 4) do not show any splitting indicating

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Compounds	Band position (cm ⁻¹)	10 Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B' (cm ⁻¹)	β (-B', B)
[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Cl ₂]	16130b	4320	799	0.776
	8547			
	5650			
[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ Br ₂]	5050b	4160	683	0.663
	15385b			
	9389			
[(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₄ N] ₂ [Ni(NCS) ₂ I ₂]	5730b	4000	653	0.633
	5050			
	14815b			
	8510			
	6135			
	5634			
	5071			

b = broad.

that the low symmetry has no effect in splitting the ν_3 band in T_d symmetry. Such a situation has also been observed in case of mixed tetrahalonickelates(II)¹³ (NiCl₂Br₂)²⁻. However, the lowest energy band in near ir region (5050-6100 cm⁻¹)

except in $[\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2\text{I}_2]^{2-}$ are rather broad, which may be assumed as consisting of split components (but not well resolved) of the ν_1 band. The highest energy band in the near ir region ($8500-9400\text{ cm}^{-1}$), appears as a single band which has been assigned to ν_2 transition in simple T_d symmetry of Ni(II).

The ligand field parameters calculated by adopting tetrahedral model using equations employed by Underhill and Billing²¹ are given in Table 4. All the parameters indicate that the crystal field strength lies in the order $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^-$. The B' values compared to that of free ion [1030 cm^{-1} for Ni(II)] suggest the presence of an appreciable orbital overlap which lie in the order $\text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A. K.) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial help.

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